

WAYS OF DEVELOPING SPIRITUAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Аннотация: The article considers the issue of improving the technologies of developing spiritual culture of future teachers in the context of modernization of the personnel training system, shows the ways of developing spiritual culture of future teachers.

Ключевые слова: culture, spiritual culture, future teacher, approaches, educational technology.

Введение.

One of the key components of social policy in our country is the improvement of the education system. The reforms being implemented in the field of education are multi-faceted, aiming to enhance the education system, modernize the content and technology of the pedagogical process, establish new forms of connection between education and practice, and update the system for preparing and retraining teaching staff. A modern approach to preparing pedagogical personnel includes the understanding that only creative, inquisitive, and experienced teachers can work effectively in this system. Currently, a new pedagogical paradigm is being shaped in the education system, based on the idea of self-worth and spirituality, affirming the priority of universal values, humanistic ideals, and spiritual values. A modern approach to the educational process includes psychological support, meaning psychological assistance from the moment a person "enters the world of education until the completion of active work."

All of this brings the issue of returning education and upbringing to the cultural context to the forefront: a cultured teacher forms a free, humanistic, spiritual, practical, and creative individual. In this regard, pedagogical research substantiates an axiological approach that considers life creativity as the highest quality of life, seeing the meaning of life in spirituality, which embodies a person's relationship with the world, knowledge, and self.

Literature Review: Research conducted by scholars has shown that the following principles should be adhered to in developing the spiritual culture of students in higher education institutions of pedagogy:

Holistic Approach – understanding students as a unity of biological and psychological, social and spiritual, conscious and self-conscious, rational and irrational elements.

Viewing students as individuals in need of pedagogical support, who require an individualized approach; this includes respecting the role of high social values in personal development, recognizing each student's individuality and uniqueness,

acknowledging their social rights and freedoms, and ensuring that the goals, objects, subjects, effectiveness indicators, and results of education are reflected in the student's personality. Students should be regarded as the main subjects of this process, and pedagogical activity should rely on anthropological knowledge.

A **differentiated approach** – the content, forms, and methods of educational work should be chosen, firstly, in connection with ethnic and regional, cultural-historical, socio-economic, and socio-psychological conditions; secondly, in accordance with the main functions of social institutions; and

thirdly, taking into account the individuality of participants in the educational process.

The **principle of harmony with nature** requires adherence to the following rules: 1) studying and educating the student's individual-personal characteristics; 2) relying on the motives and needs of students; 3) ensuring the interrelationship between psychological-pedagogical diagnostics, consultation, and correction.

The **principle of harmony with culture** involves viewing students as capable life subjects of cultural self-development and self-transformation in all education systems; viewing education as a cultural process, and the educational institution as a cultural-educational space where cultural examples of life are created, cultural events occur, and culture and cultured individuals are nurtured. In the educational process, it is essential to rely on national traditions, customs, and ceremonies.

In organizing relationships in the educational process, a **humanistic approach** is needed, including mutual respect between teachers and students, careful listening to students' opinions, and treating them with kindness and attention. It is important that developing individuals feel protected, needed, and valued. Psychological comfort should be created for the mutual influence between teachers and students aimed at achieving the same objective.

A **value-oriented approach** should aim to create the necessary conditions for students to understand the meaning of their own lives and to nurture personal thoughts that arise from their interactions with nature, society, and culture.

Developing the spiritual culture of students requires clarifying the criteria that guarantee the effectiveness of this process.

Taking into account the levels of future teachers' educational-cognitive activities, the socio-pedagogical situations that allow for the development of their spiritual culture can be classified into four groups:

- ✓ Tasks involving the search for solutions to elementary modeled problematic situations;
- ✓ Tasks involving the search for solutions to simple modeled problematic situations;
- ✓ Tasks involving the search for solutions to complex modeled problematic situations;
- ✓ Tasks involving the search for solutions to highly complex modeled problematic situations.

The local-modular technology for developing the spiritual culture of future teachers can be considered through neuro-linguistic programming technology, as well as the issue of harmonizing technogenic civilization with the development of students' spiritual culture.

Discussion and Results: Just as pedagogical technologies are essential in education, organizing the upbringing process on a technological basis is equally crucial for shaping and developing spiritual culture. One of the most important tasks in pedagogy today is updating the content of upbringing in line with the demands of the times. The significance of upbringing technology is particularly notable in this regard. Through upbringing technology, special attention is given to developing independent thinking, creativity, spirituality, and worldview in students and learners, which are key factors that enrich and shape them.

The use of pedagogical technologies in the education-upbringing process is considered an innovative approach. It reflects socio-engineering thinking in pedagogy and is associated with standardizing the teaching and upbringing process to a certain extent by creating an optimal project. For instance, if the necessity has arisen to abandon traditional lecture and oral presentation methods in teaching and organize a modern educational process through technical means, then in the upbringing process, there is also a need for different approaches based on the demands placed on today's individuals. The younger generation today, unlike the youth of the past, are developing into independent thinkers who actively and creatively participate in the progress of the times.

The technology of upbringing has its own characteristics in setting the goals of upbringing. Upbringing technology is a systematic combination of various pedagogical tools, forms, and methods designed to solve specific educational tasks. There is an adequate educational technology for solving each task, and as the task changes, so does its technology. In this process, the goals of upbringing are determined by results that are expressed, visible, and developed in the actions of students.

In upbringing technology, implementing the goals of upbringing is based on the cultivation of emotions in individuals, making it somewhat challenging to achieve precise goals. The unique characteristic of upbringing technology is that the process of upbringing is designed and implemented to guarantee the achievement of its goals. In this process, the teacher's activity is aimed at clear objectives.

Goal-orientedness, diagnostic examination of the upbringing process, dividing the process into individual influential parts, improving it, and achieving high results with minimal time investment accelerate the transformation of students from passive participants into active subjects. Planning the organization of educational influence on a technological basis requires a high level of skill from the teacher. Once all the necessary materials are prepared, the teacher primarily fulfills organizational and consultative roles.

The structure of upbringing technology aimed at developing spiritual culture includes the following:

- Developing the goals of upbringing;
- Converting the goals of upbringing into control tasks;
- Systematizing the implementation of upbringing goals;
- Methods for achieving the goals;
- Evaluating the achieved goals.

In forming and organizing the pedagogical process in upbringing technology, the following principles are fundamental:

- The principle of a holistic approach to upbringing;
- The principle of continuous upbringing;
- The principle of goal-oriented upbringing;
- The joint activity of teachers and educators.

Each of these components forms a system for applying pedagogical situations in a specific direction. The upbringing process is continuous and is shaped within the family, community, school, and higher education institutions. The foundation of upbringing technology is goal-orientedness, constant interaction with students, and comprehensive coverage of the learning process through upbringing technology.

Understanding and creatively approaching upbringing technologies, effectively using the organizational forms, tools, and methods of upbringing, and managing it are dependent on the teacher's methodological preparation. This, in turn, requires the implementation of the technology of upbringing. Because in the current era of progress, creating and applying upbringing technology in shaping the younger generation and encouraging them toward creative activity can lead to high results.

Ensuring the continuity of education and upbringing, organizing it in a systematic way, is one of the main issues in nurturing the younger generation, who are the future of our country. Strengthening attention to extracurricular activities, both during and outside of lessons, is key to achieving continuity in the education-upbringing process. The role of extracurricular educational and upbringing activities is not only to engage the youth but to strengthen the knowledge they acquire in lessons, awaken their interest in our national values, and fill their lives with joy and enthusiasm. As with the lesson process, organizing educational activities is also a crucial and responsible role for class teachers.

Based on the above, we recommend using the following educational methods based on our experience in upbringing: "Conflict method," "Round table," "Three-step interview," "Communication training," "Problem-solving method," "Pen in the center of the table," "Gallery walk," "Academic debate," "Snowstorm," "Beehive," "Critical situation analysis," and others.

To work with these technologies, it is necessary to form groups of several people, create an atmosphere of trust, and eliminate psychological tension that may hinder open discussion. These technologies aim to expand the scope of thinking, disregard existing limitations, develop cognitive activities, and intensify the process of upbringing. The goal of these technologies is to engage students and learners more actively and provide them with opportunities to learn from one another.

Advantages of Such Technologies:

1. They allow students to share more of their ideas and thoughts.
2. In small groups, students may express opinions that differ from what they would say in larger groups.
3. By sharing experiences and thoughts, students broaden their worldviews and ideas and modify existing approaches.
4. They shift the focus from the teacher (educator) to the participants.
5. They make students take more responsibility for their own upbringing.

When introducing innovations into the upbringing process and fostering motivation among students, the following should be emphasized:

- Explaining the necessity of educational influence and skills;
- Creating a sense of personal responsibility;
- Sparking and maintaining participants' interest throughout the process;
- Explaining how to apply acquired experiences in real life;
- Providing approval, recognition, and encouragement;
- Fostering healthy competition;
- Allowing discussions on how students can achieve future successes based on their learned experiences;
- Creating opportunities for active listening.

The main goal of the current upbringing system is to prepare students for independent life, teach creative thinking, and raise individuals with high-level thinking skills. In general, the educational-upbringing system, including its programs, content, and standards, is continuously improving. These rapid changes demand the creation of distinctive technologies for education and upbringing.

Only a highly skilled teacher with superior competencies can implement such rapid advancements. The main objective of today's innovative "Learn-Teach" and "Master-Apprentice" projects is to provide education to a modern, highly cultured generation. This can only be achieved by a skilled educator with intellectual potential and well-formed knowledge, skills, and expertise.

However, we often hear remarks suggesting that the introduction of upbringing technologies is somewhat lagging. The educational, upbringing, and developmental objectives of lessons must be interconnected, with each complementing the other. In the education-upbringing process, it is essential to gradually instill the rich cultural heritage, national values, and traditions of the Uzbek people into students through upbringing technologies. In organizing educational-upbringing activities, teachers must follow these pedagogical requirements:

- They must be suitable for the student's age and psychological state;
- They must serve to strengthen the knowledge acquired in lessons;
- They must be organized based on clear goals and plans;
- Through these activities, elementary students should develop moral qualities like community spirit, cooperation, and mutual help.

In conclusion, upbringing technology yields significant results in a well-formed continuous education system. The use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational-upbringing process, improving the efficiency of modern upbringing methods, and the changing work practices of teachers and educators all contribute to the transformation of the pedagogical system's upbringing aspect.

This also sets specific tasks in organizing and managing the informatization of spiritual and educational processes. Conducting purposeful educational events and continuously diagnosing them yields positive results. It is appropriate to establish the education of young people in the spirit of national independence ideals based on new pedagogical technologies within the continuous education system. The effectiveness of these efforts, and the entire education-upbringing process in the continuous education system, serve one goal: to ideologically educate students and nurture a well-rounded generation that will contribute to strengthening independence. This helps determine the level of spiritual development among future teachers.

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